

EPSTEIN BARR VIRUS AND PARKINSON'S DISEASE - A CAUSAL LINK?

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ABSTRACT. Introduction: The etiology of Parkinson's disease (PD) is still not clear. The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between Epstein Barr virus (EBV) and PD.

Methods: A systematic search of the electronic databases PubMed was conducted to identify publications exploring the relationship between EBV and PD. All statistical tests were one-sided, and statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$.

Results: Without EBV infection no PD.

Conclusions: EBV infection is a necessary condition of PD.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) or a "shaking palsy" as described by Dr. James Parkinson[55] (1755–1824) in 1817 is a neurological disease characterised by different features like difficulty in walking, resting tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity, postural instability and other symptoms. Later, Jean-Martin Charcot renamed the disease Parkinson's disease. PD prevalence increases steadily with age, a significant increase of the prevalence[62] of Parkinson's disease in the past three decades has been documented reaching about 1,903 per 100,000 in older than age 80. About 630,000 people have been diagnosed with PD in 2010 in the United States, PD prevalence is likely to double by 2040.[47] The cause of Parkinson's disease (PD) is still largely unknown. The death of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra due to unclear etiology and pathogenesis is the main pathological change of PD. Several risk factors[19], including trauma, drugs, gene, neuroinflammation, and toxicity, are related to the development of PD. A review and meta-analysis of cohort and case-control studies by Hui Wang et al. [74] of various pathogenic microorganisms like *Helicobacter pylori* (HP), hepatitis C virus (HCV), *Malassezia*, *Chlamydomyces pneumoniae*, hepatitis B virus, influenza virus, measles, varicella-zoster virus, mumps, German measles, pertussis, scarlet fever, rheumatic fever, diphtheria, cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus, herpes virus, and *Borrelia*

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burgdorferi found that infection of HP, HCV, Malassezia, C. pneumoniae might increased the risk of PD. However, the cause or at least a cause of PD is still not identified.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Data.

2.1.1. *Search strategy.* The electronic database PubMed was search February 2021. The search strategy was as follows: (Parkinson Disease[MeSH Term]) AND (EBV[MeSH Term]). Finally, the reference lists of articles checked were also searched manually to identify additional relevant studies not captured by the database search. The authors were not contacted for unpublished data. In toto, 16 Studies were unidentified. At the end, only the study of Bu et al. [24] remained to be analysed.

TABLE 1. EBV IgG positive and M. Parkinson .

		M. Parkinson		
		YES	NO	
EBV IgG positive	YES	130	137	267
	NO	1	4	5
		131	141	272

Causal relationship k =	0,0771
p Value right tailed (HGD) =	0,2090
p (SINE) =	0,9963
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE B _t) =	0,0076
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE A _t) =	0,2000
p Value (SINE) =	0,0037
p(IOI)=	0,5000
p(IOU)=	0,4632

2.1.2. *Inclusion and exclusion criteria.* The inclusion and exclusion criteria were as follows: (a) Data available in English, (b) studies on animals were excluded.

2.1.3. *Fictive control group.* The quality of the data of each included study was assessed separately by the index of unfairness or the index of independence. An unfair study design of an original study has been corrected without any influence on the statistical conclusions drawn. The data of the study of Bu et al. [24] are biased, the study design has been very unfair (p(IOU) = 0,4632). Based on an approximate prevalence of EBV within the control group of about 90 % and the assumption of a fair study design (a = d = 130), we obtain the following, reality near data (p(IOU) = 0,0).

TABLE 2. EBV IgG positive and M. Parkinson.

		M. Parkinson		
		YES	NO	
EBV IgG positive	YES	130	1300	1430
	NO	1	130	131
		131	1430	1561

Causal relationship k =	0,0833
p Value right tailed (HGD) =	0,0001
p (SINE) =	0,9994
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE B_t) =	0,0076
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE A_t) =	0,0076
p Value (SINE) =	0,0006
p(IOI)=	0,8322
p(IOU)=	0,0000

2.1.4. *Data extraction.* Data of each pathogenic microorganism of studies which reported data of infection of multiple pathogenic microorganisms were regarded as an independent study.

2.2. **Definitions.** Reaching a generally valid consensus on the definition of the numbers +0 and +1 appears to be difficult. These numbers are fundamental importance in classical logic, probability theory and so forth. The definition of the basic numbers +1 and +0 in terms of Euler's identity and physical 'constants' offer us the possibility to test classical logic or mathematical theorems et cetera by reproduce-able physical experiments too. In particular, it is very remarkable that Leibniz [50] himself published in 1703 the first self-consistent binary number system representing all numeric values while using typically +0 (zero) and +1 (one).

2.2.1. *The number +0.*

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum [31, 71, 76, 77], let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number [22]. The number +0 is defined as the expression

$$(2.1) \quad +0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv +1 + i^2 \equiv +1 + e^{i\pi} \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) + e^{i\pi}$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign [64] or equality sign [66] used to indicate equality and '-' [54, 79] denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus [64] signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) [27] or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity [33] is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations [80]. In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity [33] is logically sound and correct.

2.2.2. The number +1.

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). Again, let c denote the speed of light in vacuum [31, 71, 76, 77], let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number [22]. The number +1 is defined as the expression

$$(2.2) \quad +1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv -i^2 \equiv -e^{i\pi} \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign [64] or equality sign [66] used to indicate equality and '-' [54, 79] denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus [64] signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

2.2.3. Two by two table of Bernoulli random variables.

Definition 2.3 (Two by two table of Bernoulli random variables).

The two by two or contingency table as introduced by Karl Pearson[57] in 1904 harbours a large variety of topics and debates. Central to these is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences that extrapolate from sample data to general facts. However, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between two *Bernoulli*[20] (*i. e. +0/+1*) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* [73] (period of time) t . In this context, let a Bernoulli distributed random variable A_t denote a risk factor, a condition or a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* [73] (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In the case of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$(2.3) \quad \begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(A_t) \end{aligned}$$

Let a Bernoulli distributed random variable B_t denote an outcome, a conditioned event or an effect and occur or exist et cetera with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . It is

$$(2.4) \quad \begin{aligned} E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(B_t) \end{aligned}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.5) \quad E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.6) \quad E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.7) \quad E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.8) \quad E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

In general, it is

$$(2.9) \quad p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1$$

Table 3 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

TABLE 3. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.4. *Two by two table of Binomial random variables.***Definition 2.4 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).**

Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is **constant** from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.10) \quad A &= N \times E(A_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(A_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.11) \quad B &= N \times E(B_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(B_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

where N denotes the population size. Furthermore, it is

$$(2.12) \quad a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t))$$

and

$$(2.13) \quad b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t))$$

and

$$(2.14) \quad c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t))$$

and

$$(2.15) \quad d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t))$$

and

$$(2.16) \quad a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N$$

Table 4 provide us again an overview of a two by two table of Binomial random variables.

TABLE 4. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		A
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

2.2.5. *Independence.***Definition 2.5 (Independence).**

In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t *at the same* Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence [46, 52] in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of) time t (i. e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$(2.17) \quad p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t)$$

2.2.6. *Dependence.***Definition 2.6 (Dependence).**

The dependence of events [3, p. 57-61] is defined as

$$(2.18) \quad p\left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n}$$

2.2.7. *Exclusion relationship.***Definition 2.7 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).**

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined [3, p. 68-70] as

$$(2.19) \quad \begin{aligned} p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the Henry M. Sheffer, 1913 relationship, it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 5).

TABLE 5. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) A_t	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43.538 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine} : \text{BNT162b2} \mid \text{COVID} - 19(\text{infection})) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 (2.20) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538}\right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981625
 \end{aligned}$$

with a P Value = 0,000184.

2.2.8. *The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship.*

Definition 2.8 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t \mid B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \mid B_t) \mid A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 (2.21) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}
 \end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \mid B_t) \mid B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 (2.22) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}
 \end{aligned}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t \mid B_t)$,

in which case the null hypothesis to be accepted. Yate's [82] continuity correction has not been used under these circumstances.

2.2.9. *The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship.*

Definition 2.9 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$(2.23) \quad \begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)} \end{aligned}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.2.10. *Neither nor conditions.*

Definition 2.10 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [*NOR*]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (rejection, Jean Nicod's statement 1924) relationship (*NOR*), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined [3, p. 68-70] as

$$(2.24) \quad \begin{aligned} p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.11. *The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship.*

Definition 2.11 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$(2.25) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \\ &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0 \end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \\
 (2.26) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Yate's [82] continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.12. *The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship.*

Definition 2.12 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\
 (2.27) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}
 \end{aligned}$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 6).

TABLE 6. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.2.13. *Necessary condition.*

Definition 2.13 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined [3, p. 15-28] as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 (2.28) \quad &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

It is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (see Table 7).

TABLE 7. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$+0$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$+1$

Remark 2.3. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur [3–8, 13–17].

Example. A human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition of human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition of human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

2.2.14. *The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship.*

Definition 2.14 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert [39] and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson [56] in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.29) \quad \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t \mid B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
&\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}
\end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.30) \quad \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t \mid \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
&\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
\end{aligned}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's [82] continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.15. *The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship.*

Definition 2.15 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.31) \quad pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\
&\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)}
\end{aligned}$$

2.2.16. *Sufficient condition.*

Definition 2.16 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined[3, p. 68-70] as

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.32) \quad p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

It is $p(A_t > -B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 8).

TABLE 8. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$+0$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$+1$

Remark 2.4. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred [3–8, 13–17]. **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during a heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will be wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not to become wet even during a heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event which can counteract the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an anti-dot of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$(2.33) \quad p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.2.17. *The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship.*

Definition 2.17 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 (2.34) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A}
 \end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | \underline{B}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b+d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \frac{((a+c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 (2.35) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}
 \end{aligned}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis accepted. Yate's [82] continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.18. *The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship.*

Definition 2.18 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.36) \qquad pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.2.19. *Necessary and sufficient conditions.*

Definition 2.19 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined[3, p. 68-70] as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\
 (2.37) \quad &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2.20. *The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship.*

Definition 2.20 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 (2.38) \quad &\frac{d - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 (2.39) \quad &\frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level

of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's [82] continuity correction should be used at all.

2.2.21. *The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship.*

Definition 2.21 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$(2.40) \quad \begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)} \end{aligned}$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 9 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

TABLE 9. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.2.22. *Either or conditions.*

Definition 2.22 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t >-< B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined[3, p. 68-70] as

$$(2.41) \quad \begin{aligned} p(A_t >-< B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{b+c}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned}$$

It is $p(A_t >-< B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t <-> B_t)$ (see Table 10).

TABLE 10. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.2.23. *The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship.*

Definition 2.23 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t > - < B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 (2.42) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{A}
 \end{aligned}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 (2.43) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{B}
 \end{aligned}$$

Yate's [82] continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.24. *The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship.*

Definition 2.24 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [12] of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2.44) \qquad pValue_{lt}(A_t > - < B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t > - < B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.2.25. Causal relationship k .

Definition 2.25 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal relationship [3–6, 8] between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined at each single Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$(2.45) \quad \begin{aligned} k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t . Table 11 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

TABLE 11. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.2.26. Cause and effect.

Definition 2.26 (Cause and effect).

What is the cause, what is the effect? Under conditions of a **positive** causal relationship k , an event U_t which is for sure a cause of another event W_t is at the same time t a necessary and sufficient condition of an event W_t . Table 12 may illustrate this relationship.

TABLE 12. What is the cause, what is the effect?

		Effect W_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause U_t	TRUE	+1	+0	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	+0	+1	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

The collapse and the logical inconsistency of the risk ratio under these circumstances is obvious.

As can be seen, there is a kind of strange mirroring between U_t and W_t . Lastly, both are converses of each other too. In other words, U_t 's being a necessary condition of W_t 's is equivalent to W_t 's being a sufficient condition of U_t 's (and vice versa). In general, it is

$$(2.46) \quad (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \equiv (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t) \equiv ((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \equiv +1$$

In our everyday words,

without

U_t

no

W_t

is equivalent with

if

W_t

then

U_t

and vice versa.

Necessary and sufficient conditions are relationships used to describe the relationship between two events at the same Bernoulli trial t . In more detail, if U_t then W_t is equivalent with W_t is necessary for U_t , because the truth of U_t guarantees the truth of W_t . In general, it is

$$(2.47) \quad (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t) \equiv ((\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \wedge (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t)) \equiv +1$$

In other words, it is impossible to have U_t without W_t [21]. Similarly, U_t is sufficient for W_t , because U_t being true always implies that W_t is true, but U_t not being true does not always imply that W_t is not true.

For instance, **without** gaseous oxygen (U_t), there would be **no** burning wax candle (W_t); hence the relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is equally true and given.

This simple example may illustrate the reason why a sufficient condition alone is not enough to describe a cause completely. The relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is given. Independently of this fact, a burning wax candle is not the cause of gaseous oxygen. Therefore, in order to be a cause of oxygen, additional evidence is necessary that a burning wax candle is a necessary condition of gaseous oxygen too. However, even if the relationship **without** gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle is given, this relationship is not given vice versa. The relationship **without** burning wax candle **no** gaseous oxygen is not given. Like other fundamental concepts, the concepts of cause and effect can be associated with difficulties too. In order to recognise a causal relationship between U_t and W_t , it is necessary that the same study or that at least different studies provide evidence of a necessary condition between U_t and W_t and of a sufficient condition between U_t and W_t and if possible of **a necessary and sufficient condition** between U_t and W_t too.

Mathematically, a necessary and sufficient condition between U_t and W_t is defined as

$$(2.48) \quad (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv +1$$

However, I think it necessary to make a clear distinction between a necessary and sufficient condition and the converse relationship (Eq. 2.46) above.

$$(2.49) \quad ((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \neq (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t)$$

2.2.27. *Study design and bias.* Systematic observation and experimentation, inductive and deductive reasoning are essential for any formation and testing of hypotheses and theories about the natural world. In one way or another, logically and mathematically sound scientific methods and concepts are crucial constituents of any scientific progress. When all goes well, different scientists at different times and places using the same scientific methodology should be able to generate the same scientific knowledge. However, more than half (52%) of scientists surveyed believe that studies do not successfully reproduce sufficiently similar or the same results as the original studies [2]. In a very large study on publication bias in meta-analyses, Kicinski et al. [44] found evidence of publication bias even in systematic reviews. Therefore, a careful re-evaluation of the study/experimental design, the statistical methods and other scientific means which underpin scientific inquiry and research goals appears to be necessary once and again. While it is important to recognise the shortcoming of today's science, one issue which has shaped debates over studies published is the question: **has a study really measured what it set out to?** Even if studies carried out can vary greatly in detail the data from the studies itself provide information about the credibility of the data.

Definition 2.27 (Index of unfairness).

The index of unfairness [10] (IOU) is defined as

$$(2.50) \quad p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{n} \right) - 1 \right)$$

A very good study design should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In point of fact against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOU})$, a $p(\text{IOU})$ up to 0.25 could be of use too. An index of unfairness is of use to proof whether sample data are biased and whether sample data can be used for Chi-square based analysis of necessary conditions, of sufficient conditions and of causal relationships.

Definition 2.28 (Index of independence).

The index of independence[9] (IOI) is defined as

$$(2.51) \quad p(\text{IOI}(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+\underline{B}}{n} \right) - 1 \right)$$

A very good study design which aims to prove **an exclusion relationship or a causal relationship** should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. However once again, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOI})$, sample data with a $p(\text{IOI})$ up to 0.25 are of use too. Today, most double-blind placebo-controlled studies are based on the demand that **$p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$** while the value of $p(\text{IOU})$ or of $p(\text{IOI})$ has been widely neglected. Such an approach leads to unnecessary big sample sizes, the increase of cost, the waste of time and, most importantly of all, to epistemological systematically biased sample data and conclusions drawn. A change is necessary.

2.3. Proof methods. Considered from the historical point of view, human reasoning and knowledge appears to be to some extent relative too. Although it seems almost impossible, to prove or to establish the correctness of a statement, a theorem, a theory once and for all, this does not justify any technical or other errors in (human) reasoning which are many times identified the hard way but easy to overlook while in contrast to that **charges and proofs of fallacious reasoning always need time, money, and personal dignity to be accepted by the scientific community.**

**“Niemals aber kann die Wahrheit einer Theorie erwiesen werden.
Denn niemals weiß man,
daß auch in Zukunft eine Erfahrung bekannt werden wird,
die Ihren Folgerungen widerspricht...”**

[32]

Albert Einstein’s position translated into English: ‘But the truth of a theory can never be proven. For one never knows if future experience will contradict its conclusion; and furthermore there are always other conceptual systems imaginable which might coordinate the very same facts. ‘Often, our fear of the unknown appears to overshadow our mind to an objectively unjustified extent. However, logically sound scientific verification and proof techniques are likely to allow us to continue our successful and rapid identification of contradictory scientific findings and are appropriate enough to shed some light even on this unknown. Step by step, by following the time honoured principle of going **from the known (and secured) to the unknown (and unsecured)** we will bring more light into the epistemological darkness which may surround us sometimes. Following Einstein, a theory can very well be found to be incorrect if there is a logical error in its deduction.

**“Eine Theorie kann also wohl als unrichtig erkannt werden,
wenn in ihren Deduktionen
ein logischer Fehler ist ...”**

[32]

In other words, grain by grain and the hen fills her belly. Scientific proof methods are **a demarcation line between science and non-science** [59]. In this context, the development of new suitable scientific experimental and non-experimental test methods is of key scientific value. It may be allowed to point out view of these numerous scientific proof [11] methods.

2.3.1. *Proof by counter example.*

Definition 2.29 (Proof by counter example). Scientific progress can be achieved not only through doing things right, but also by correcting (scientific) mistakes. Both contributions of authors are equivalent to each other and the two sides of the same coin. A **proof by counter example** is a valid scientific proof technique with the potential to correct horrific and dreadful scientific mistakes especially in philosophy, mathematics and science as such.

**“No amount of experimentation
can ever prove me right;
a single experiment
can prove me wrong.”**
[65]

In particular, the close investigation of counter examples can give us an insight into the many deep and delicate issues surrounding a statement or theorem. A generally valid theorem can refuted by a single counter example [18, 26, 43, 51, 65, 67, 70, 75] by showing an instance where a given statement, theorem et cetera cannot possibly be correct.

It is worth to emphasise in this context that **one single counter example** refutes a theorem, a theory, a conjecture **as effectively as n** counter examples.

2.3.2. *Proof by (thought) experiments.*

Unfortunately, too often, competing scientific positions or even theories of the nature or of our world are excluding each other. A (theoretical) scientific verification becomes pressing while (thought) experiments are of special importance in this context. In short, Albert Einstein wrote in a letter to the student J. S. Switzer on April 23th, 1953, **Albert Einstein** the following:

“Development of Western **science** is based on two great achievements: the invention of the formal **logical** system (in Euclidean geometry) by the Greek philosophers, **and** the discovery of the possibility to find out **causal relationships** by systematic **experiment** (during the Renaissance). ”
[42]

In other words, (thought) experiments are one of the methods to proof theorems and theories.

2.3.3. *Modus tollens*. From a practical point of view, various proposals [17] have been put forward which criteria of demarcation between science and non-science should be applied, including **modus tollens** as advocated especially by **Karl Popper**. Following Popper,

“... it is possible by means of purely deductive inferences
(with the help of the modus tollens of classical logic)
to argue
from the truth of singular statements
to the falsity of universal statements.”
[58]

2.3.4. *Proof by modus inversus*. It is noticeable that our today’s methods of investigation especially in natural sciences and even the knowledge achieved relies to a very great extent on mathematics and mathematical rules too. Thus far, mathematics as such appears to enjoy a very special esteem within scientific community and is regarded more or less as above all other sciences [17]. This view is sometimes further strengthened by the common believe that the laws or mathematics are absolutely certain and indisputable. However, it is noteworthy that objects studied in mathematics are not all the time located in space and time and the methods of investigation of mathematics differ sometimes markedly from the methods of investigation in the natural sciences [17]. Therefore, first and after all and in a slightly different way, **today’s mathematics itself is more or less a product of human thought and mere human imagination** and belongs as such to a world of human thought and mere human imagination. In point of fact, **human thought and mere human imagination which produces the laws of mathematics is able to produce erroneous or incorrect results too** with the principal consequence that even mathematics or **mathematical theorems, rules or other results valid since thousands of years are in constant danger of being overthrown by newly discovered facts** [17]. **Modus inversus** [11, 17, 72] is a suitable proof method to check mathematical position and theorems for logical consistency.

However, **modus inversus** is an additional approach to solve the problem of (see also: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4165074>) demarcation between science and non-science. In contrast to **modus ponens**, **modus inversus is designed primarily to preserve at all costs the contradiction**, the falsity, the falseness, the falsehood as such. In contrast to the principle *ex contradictione sequitur quodlibet* [25, 60, 61], **from a contradictory premise or a contradictory statement like $(+1=+0)$, does not anything follow but the contradiction itself**. In other words, in the absence of (technical and other) errors, **the contradiction is preserved**. In particular, even if one of the main tasks of *modus inversus* [11] is to preserve the contradiction under any circumstances, the main task of *modus inversus* is to recognise the truth too. The abstract structure of *modus inversus* is as follows.

Proof by modus inversus. Thus far, let ${}_R P_t$ denote a premise at a certain point in (space-) time t . Let ${}_R C_t$ denote the conclusion at the same certain point in (space-) time t .

Premises.

- (1) If $({}_R P_t$ is false) then $({}_R C_t$ is false).
 (2) ${}_R P_t$ is false.

Conclusion.

- (3) ${}_R C_t$ is false. □

The following 2x2 table may illustrate modus inversus again. Let ${}_R P_t$ denote a premise from the standpoint of a stationary observer, a Bernoulli distributed random variable at a certain period of time or Bernoulli trial t [73].

TABLE 13. Modus inversus

		Conclusion ${}_R C_t$	
		FALSE	TRUE
Premisse ${}_R P_t$	FALSE	+1	+0
	TRUE	+1	+1
			+1

In terms of probability theory modus inversus can be expressed as follows.

TABLE 14. Modus inversus II

		Conclusion ${}_R C_t$		
		FALSE	TRUE	
Premisse ${}_R P_t$	FALSE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p({}_R P_t)$
	TRUE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p({}_R P_t)$
		$p({}_R C_t)$	$p({}_R C_t)$	+1

The premise takes only the values ${}_R P_t$ either +0 or +1. Let ${}_R C_t$ denote a conclusion from the standpoint of a stationary observer R , a Bernoulli distributed random variable at the same period of time or Bernoulli trial t . The conclusion ${}_R C_t$ itself can take only the values ${}_R C_t$ either +0 or +1. Under conditions of classical logic, +0 may denote false while +1 may denote true. The modus inversus is defined as if (premise _{t} is false) then (conclusion _{t} is false). Formally, modus inversus can be expressed as

$$(2.52) \quad ({}_R P_t) \cup ({}_R \neg C_t) \equiv +1$$

while the sign \cup denotes inclusive or. It is noticeable and by far not regrettable that according to modus inversus **it is not possible to achieve a true conclusion while starting with a false premise**. The follow-up question should be: what allows the assumption that modus inversus is generally valid or valid at all?

Example: Burning candle experiment

A simple to perform real-world experiment may illustrate the general validity of modus

inversus. Let A_t denote gaseous oxygen, a Binomial random variable, which can take only two values, either gaseous oxygen present = +1 or gaseous oxygen not present = +0. Gaseous oxygen is present means that the amount of gaseous oxygen is enough to assure that a candle can burn. Let B_t denote a candle, a Binomial random variable, which can take only two values, either a candle is burning = +1 or a candle is not burning = +0.

In this experiment, an investigator lights the candle wick of some candles (old, you, big, small, red, green, curved, straight et cetera) under different conditions. As next, candle flame reacts with gaseous oxygen such that light and heat which characterises a candle are produced. The data as obtained by this real world experiment are illustrated by the following 2x2 table.

TABLE 15. Example. Modus inversus III

		Candle is burning	
		FALSE	TRUE
Gaseous	FALSE	+1	+0
oxygen	TRUE	+1	+1
		+1	

The relationship between gaseous oxygen and the behaviour of a candle produced out of simple wax is studied to demonstrate the relationship of modus inversus to objective reality. In other words, modus inversus is backed by natural processes independent of human mind and consciousness.

For this reason, and especially if different persons with different ideology and believe are aiming to arrive at the same logical conclusions with regard to such a difficult topic as indeterminate forms are, they will have to agree at least upon some view fundamental laws (axioms) as well as the methods by which other laws can be deduced therefrom. At this point, clarifying some fundamental axioms or starting points of investigations can therefore be essential part of every scientific method and any scientific progress.

2.3.5. *Direct proof.* The truth or falsehood of a given theorem can be demonstrated too by a straightforward combination of established facts.

2.3.6. *Proof by contradiction.* Proof by contradiction [30, 81] is a widely used proof method and goes back at least as far as to ancient times. The truth or the validity of a theorem can be established by **assuming that a statement or a theorem we want to prove is false**. In the following of the proof by showing that such an assumption leads to a contradiction it is justified to conclude that we were wrong to assume the theorem was false. In other words, the theorem must be true.

2.3.7. *Proof by other methods.* There are of course many other scientific proof methods which can be found in literature.

2.3.8. *Statistical methods.* The necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion condition relationship, the causal relationship *k et cetera* and other statistical methods were used to evaluate the relationship between the events/factors analysed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a necessary condition distribution in the population, a sufficient condition distribution in the population, a necessary and sufficient condition distribution in the population, an exclusion distribution in the population *et cetera*. Identifying and avoiding bias in research is of fundamental importance. The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence and IOU, the index of unfairness. The sample size was sufficient enough in order for the chi-square approximation to be used. The hyper-geometric distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship *k*. All statistical analyses were performed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). A P-value $<.05$ were considered statistically significant.

2.4. Axioms.

2.4.1. *Axiom I. Lex identitatis.* Backed by thousands of years of often bitter human experience, the scientific development has taught us all that human knowledge is relative too. Even if experiments and other suitable proofs are of help to encourage us more and more in our belief of the correctness of a theory, it is difficult to proof the correctness of a theorem or of a theory et cetera once and for all.

**“Niemals aber kann die Wahrheit einer Theorie erwiesen werden.
Denn niemals weiß man,
daß auch in Zukunft eine Erfahrung bekannt werden wird,
die Ihren Folgerungen widerspricht...”**
[32]

Albert Einstein’s position translated into English: ‘But the truth of a theory can never be proven. For one never knows if future experience will contradict its conclusion; and furthermore there are always other conceptual systems imaginable which might coordinate the very same facts. ’However, another remark of Einstein is worth being considered.

**“No amount of experimentation
can ever prove me right;
a single experiment
can prove me wrong.”**
[65]

In the light of the foregoing it is clear that appropriate axioms and conclusions derived from the same are a main logical foundation of any ‘theory’.

**“Grundgesetz (Axiome)
und
Folgerungen
zusammen bilden das was man
eine ‘Theorie’
nennt. ”**
[32]

Albert Einstein’s (1879-1955) message translated into English as: *Basic law (axioms) and conclusions together form what is called a ‘theory’* has still to get round. However, an axiom as a free creation of the human mind which precedes all science should be like all other axioms, as simple as possible and as self-evident as possible.

In this context, we define axiom I as

$$(2.53) \quad + 1 = +1$$

Historically, Aristotle himself already cited **the law of excluded middle** and **the law of contradiction** as examples of axioms. However, **lex identitatis** is an axiom too, which possess the potential to serve as the most basic and equally as the most simple axiom of science. Something which is really just itself is equally different from everything else. In point of fact, is such an equivalence which everything has to itself inherent or must the same be constructed by human mind and consciousness. Can and how can something be **identical with itself** [35, 37, 45, 53] and in the same respect different from itself. An increasingly popular view on identity is the one advocated by Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716):

“**Chaque chose est ce qu’elle est.**
Et dans autant d’exemples qu’on voudra
A est A,
B est B. ”
 [49]

or **A = A, B = B** or **+1 = +1**. Exactly in complete compliance with Leibniz, Johann Gottlieb Fichte (1762 - 1814) elaborates on this subject as follows:

“**Each thing is what it is ;**
it has those realities which are posited when it is posited,
(A = A.) ”
 [34]

2.4.2. *Axiom II. Lex contradictionis.* In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$(2.54) \quad + 0 = +1$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated. Thus far, axiom II is of no minor importance too. Scientist inevitably have false beliefs and make mistakes. In order to prevent scientific results from falling into logical inconsistency or logical absurdity, it is necessary to possess among other the methodological possibility to start a reasoning with a contradiction too. However and in contrast to the way of reasoning with inconsistent premises as proposed by para-consistent logic [25, 28, 29, 60, 61, 63], in the absence of technical and other errors of reasoning, the contradiction itself need to be preserved. In other words, **from a contradiction does not anything follows but the contradiction itself** while the theoretical question is indeed justified “What is so Bad about Contradictions?” [60]. Historically, **the principle of (deductive)**

explosion, coined by 12th-century French philosopher William of Soissons, demand us to accept that anything, including its own negation, can be proven or can be inferred from a contradiction. Respecting the principle of explosion, the existence of a contradiction (or the existence of logical inconsistency) in a scientific theorem, rule et cetera is disastrous. However, the historical development of science shows that scientist inevitably revise the theories, false positions and claims are identified once and again, and we all make different kind of mistakes. In order to avert a disproportionately great damage on science and to prevent reducing science into pure subjective belief, a negation of the principle of explosion is required. Nonetheless, a justified negation of **the ex contradictione quodlibet principle** [25] does not imply the correctness of paraconsistent logic [25,28,29,60,61,63] as such as advocated especially by the Peruvian philosopher Francisco Miró Quesada [63] and other [25, 28, 29, 60, 61]. In general, scientific theories appear to progress from lower and simpler to higher and more complex levels. However, high level theories cannot be taken for granted because high level theories are grounded on a lot of assumptions, definitions and other procedures and may rest upon too much erroneous stuff even if still not identified. Therefore, it should be considered to check at lower at simpler levels like with like.

In philosophy, **the principle of explosion** or the principle of Pseudo-Scotus (Latin: **ex contradictione (sequitur) quodlibet**) demand us to accept that from falsehood or from a contradiction, any statement can be proven or anything may follow. However, scientist inevitably have false beliefs and make mistakes. In order to prevent us from falling into logical inconsistency or logical absurdity, it is necessary to posses the possibility to start a reasoning with a contradiction too. However and in contrast to the way of reasoning with inconsistent premises as proposed by para-consistent logic [25, 28, 29, 60, 61, 63], in the absence of technical and other errors of reasoning, the contradiction itself need to be preserved. In other words, **from a contradiction does not anything follows but the contradiction itself**.

2.4.3. *Axiom III. Lex negationis.*

$$(2.55) \quad \neg(0) \times 0 = 1$$

where \neg denotes (logical [23] or natural) negation [1,35,36,38,40,41,45,48,53,68,69,78]. In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Without an Epstein-Barr virus infection no Parkinson's disease.

The null hypothesis 3.1.1. *The sample data support the null hypothesis that the relationship*

Without

an Epstein-Barr virus infection

no

Parkinson's disease.

is given within the population and do not support the alternative hypothesis.

The alternative hypothesis 3.1.1. *The sample data do support the alternative hypothesis that the relationship*

Without

an Epstein-Barr virus infection

no

Parkinson's disease.

is not given within the population and do not support the null hypothesis.

Proof by induction / experiment / case control study et cetera. The original data published by Bu et al. [24] (see table 1) support the Null-Hypothesis, without an EBV infection no PD ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,996324$; $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,4632$). As can be seen, these data are biased ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,4632$). Correcting the study design bias of these data (table 2) we obtain a clear result ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9994$; $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,0000$) while the causal relationship k is positive and highly significant. In other words, without an EBV infection, no PD.

□

4. DISCUSSION

Based on optical criteria, the data presented and meta-analyzed by Wang et al. [74] do not support any relationship between PD and an infection with HP, HCV, HBV, Malassezia, C. pneumoniae, chicken pox, German measles, influenza virus, mumps, measles, pertussis, and scarlet fever. At this point, it cannot be excluded completely, due to optical criteria, that herpes virus and CMV could be related with PD. All statistically based conclusions imply a level of uncertainty as they are founded on sample-based data and can be expected to be biased to a limited extent. However, the data of Bu et al. [24] (see table 1 and table 2) support the Null-Hypothesis, without an EBV infection no PD. In other words, **an EBV infection is a necessary condition of PD.**

In point of fact and as a straightforward consequence, no lumbar puncture performed should be EBV negative by IgG, PCR, et cetera assumed there is no sampling error and the diagnosis PD is given absolutely for sure.

5. CONCLUSION

An Epstein-Barr virus infection is an emerging feature in the pathology of Parkinson's disease.

In other words, without an Epstein-Barr virus infection no Parkinson's disease. It is possible, that EBV is the cause of PD.

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7. TRANSPARENCY DECLARATIONS

The author declare that no conflicts of interest can be reported regarding the present study.

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